

DATA NOTE

Thermal efficiency dataset around Cuban seas (TEDACS)

[version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 3 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

Currently, the generation of electrical energy in Cuba is supported by oil and natural gas. These sources, as it is known, are directly linked to large emissions of pollutants that are released into the environment. Therefore, it is necessary to search for new energy options that are directed towards sustainable development, allowing the preservation of natural ecosystems. Owing to the location and geographical characteristics of Cuba, it is necessary to assess the energy possibilities of the seas that surround it and to search for the most feasible areas to obtain energy from the sea temperature. This renewable energy source, in addition to being used to generate electricity, can also be used in derived technologies, such as desalination, refrigeration, and aquaculture.

Hence, a dataset is presented with the calculation of the thermal efficiency for the exploitation of thermal energy from the sea, which is based on the thermal gradient between the sea potential temperatures between the shore and the level of depth being analyzed. Outputs of 27 years of daily data from the Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS) GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product with a spatial resolution of 1/12° were used. The calculation was made using a Python script of the daily thermal efficiency at depths of 763, 902, and 1062 m, as

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these are the levels that are traditionally studied for the exploitation of sea thermal energy. In this way, 27 files of each level were generated for a total of 81 files in text format separated by commas. Each file is presented with the date, level, coordinates, and thermal efficiency. The dataset is available from the Science Data Bank repository (<https://doi.org/10.57760/sciencedb.10037>).

Keywords

Thermal efficiency, OTEC technologies, Sea thermal energy, Sea Surface Temperature

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Introduction

Ocean thermal energy conversion (OTEC) is a renewable energy technology that harnesses the solar energy absorbed by oceans to generate electricity. Heat from the sun warms surface water more than deep ocean water, creating a naturally available temperature gradient in the ocean. OTEC uses warm sea surface water with a temperature of approximately 25°C to vaporize a working fluid, which has a low boiling point, such as ammonia and propane. The vapor expands and turns a turbine coupled with a generator to produce electricity¹. The steam was then cooled with seawater that has been pumped up from the deepest layer of the ocean, where the temperature was approximately 5°C.

Thermal efficiency is the amount of heat/power used in a Rankine cycle for converting oceanic thermal energy into electrical energy². Among the different approaches used for the analysis of thermal energy efficiency, an approach based on a theoretical limit is used to maximize the efficiency of an OTEC system by converting the heat stored in the warm surface waters of the oceans into mechanical work¹.

According to previous studies, the temperature of the sea surface around Cuba oscillates throughout the year between 26° and 30°, on average. These characteristics indicate the convenience of studying the thermal energy of the seas around Cuba³.

The present work exposes the main features of a dataset that contains the computation of thermal efficiency in the seas surrounding Cuba between latitudes 18.5° and 24.0° and longitudes -73.5° and -85.5°. The objective is to evaluate the study area according to the requirements for obtaining thermal energy from the sea, which must reach values greater than or equal to 0.7 of thermal efficiency⁴. For the computation, 27 years of global ocean reanalysis data from the GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product of the Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS) with a spatial resolution of 1/12° were used⁵.

With this dataset presented, it is also possible to develop other investigations in the study area to advance the knowledge of the thermal energy potential of the sea to investigate the selection of sites where OTEC plants can be built for the generation of electrical energy, desalination seawater, and other applications.

In the following sections, the methods are presented, which introduce the study area, equation for calculating thermal efficiency, dataset with its structure, generated files, and availability of data.

Methods

This study was performed using the output `cmems_mod_glo_phy_my_0.083_P1D-m`, available for free download from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030/services), that simulates the global ocean

at 1/12° (approximately 8 km) resolution⁵, using the space-time evolution of the 3D thermodynamic variables temperature and salinity (T, S) at 4 levels: -0.49, -763.33, -902.34 and -1062.44 m. Were downloaded 27 years of these files with the “`motuclient-python`” tool⁶, which were then manipulated and analyzed with the CDO `adisit` function⁷, to calculate the temperature in situ from potential temperature and salinity data. The calculations of the maximum efficiency and the generation of the maximum, annual, and seasonal efficiency maps for each level were performed using Python version 3.9 (RRID: SCR_008394) of Python language. Therefore, the presented dataset contains the computation of thermal efficiency in the seas surrounding Cuba between latitudes 18.5° and 24.0° and longitudes -73.5° and -85.5°⁴.

Brief characterization of the study area

The study area is influenced by the marine current systems that surround it: The Caribbean current, which extends from the arc of the Lesser Antilles to the vicinity of the Yucatan Peninsula; the Yucatan Current, which connects the Caribbean Sea and the Gulf of Mexico; the Loop Current, a flow that joins the Yucatan current and the La Florida current in the eastern part of the Gulf of Mexico; and the Florida Current, from the Straits of Florida to Cape Hatteras, and is considered the beginning of the Gulf Stream. Trend studies have observed that marine flow in the Caribbean Sea has had a slight decrease in magnitude, while in the Gulf of Mexico and the Near Atlantic, there has been a subtle increase⁸.

In this area, the average temperature of the sea surface oscillates between 25 and 30°, with a minimum in February and a maximum in September. The maxima are found over deep waters in the area of the Casilda-Cazones Gulf and south of Isla de la Juventud, towards the central and northern Caribbean area, as well as another maximum north of the western coasts. Extreme minimum values were recorded in the Gulf of Mexico area, with 24° and maximum values of up to 31°. Calculation of the sea surface temperature trend with the reanalysis data used in this research revealed an increase between 0.5° and 2.5° (Figure 1).

The area is also affected by teleconnection events such as the NAO and ENSO, showing a zonal pattern in the correlation between the sea surface temperature and the NAO index six months before the development of the negative and positive phases of the event⁹. In addition, extreme phenomena such as hurricanes and cold fronts affect the Cuban archipelago every year, highlighting the relationship between the intensity of these phenomena and the different phases of the NAO and ENSO¹⁰. Figure 2 a shows the annual spatial distribution of sea surface temperature (SST) in Cuban waters, while Figure 2 b and c show the seasonal spatial distribution.

Bathymetric characterization

Cuba is geographically located in the American Mediterranean, between longitudes 74°7'52" W and 84°54'57" W, and latitudes 19°49'36" N and 23°17'9" N (Figure 3). It is bordered to the north by the Gulf of Mexico, Florida Strait, St. Nicholas

Figure 1. SST trend from GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product, 1993–2018⁵.

Channel, and old Bahama Channel; to the south by the western Caribbean Sea and Strait of Columbus; to the west by the Yucatan Channel; and to the east by the Windward Passage¹¹. The westernmost and northernmost island platforms contain the Guanahacabibes Gulf, with depths of 5–25m. Less than 1 mile from the outer edge, the shelf's insular slope drops steeply from 10 to 100m. Reefs appear parallel to the coast, cut by numerous ravines, and pass between the 5 and 10m isobaths, which form a chain that obstructs access to the coast. Continuing along the western north of the Cuban archipelago, the insular slope presents an abrupt, steep, and sinuous drop, very close to the coast, which causes the 200m isobath to be frequently found less than 1 mile from the slope.

The island platform, in the northern central zone (from Punta Hicacos to Punta Maternillos), is wide, and its edge generally registers depths between 10–25m; outside the edge of the platform, the depths increase sharply, so the island slope varies from 20–200m depth in less than 1m of distance. Above this island platform, the most continuous and extensive coral barrier in Cuba extends, with depths of less than 10m and in many places less than 5m, with cays and heads that emerge. In the northeastern area (from Nuevititas Bay to Punta Maisí), the island platform, less than 10m in depth, has an edge of 3 miles from the coast. Outside the island shore, there are no shallows, heads, or reefs that are dangerous to navigation, and the depths increase abruptly; the 200m isobath crosses within one mile of the border throughout the entire region¹².

Continuing along the southeastern area, the entire coast is bordered by a low strait of less than 20m depth, whose edge corresponds to the vertical slope that the Eastern Trench presents

in this part of the coast. The 200m isobath crosses very close to the coast, over an underwater relief that reaches great depths to the south, so the island platform of the Island of Cuba becomes very narrow, and the slope falls abruptly towards abyssal depths where it is located. The Eastern trench reaches 7,239m depth. Further to the west south, in the approaches to the Guacanayabo Gulf from the sea, the depths are great and the 200m isobath crosses 1.6 miles southwest of Cay Cruz. The isobath is the edge of the island platform, made up of coral reefs submerged at a depth of 20–40m. Among these reefs, depths are generally less than 20m, with a gentle slope¹².

Continuing westwards to the south, the Ana María Gulf is separated from the Guacanayabo Gulf by the cays Mate and Laberinto de las Doce Leguas (Figure 3); and to the southwest it is limited by the barrier reef of the Jardines de la Reina Archipelago, which extends 118 miles to the northwest with depths mostly less than 5m. The greatest distance between the edge of the platform and the coral reef barrier does not exceed 2 miles. Beyond this, the depths are abyssal, located at distances between 16 and 20 miles, with depths of 22–58m. From the Punta María Aguilar to the Cazonés Gulf, the shallow area at less than 10m depth that borders the coast is very narrow, and there are places where the cliffed coast falls directly to greater depths. Depths of 100m were recorded 2 miles from the coast and 2,000m in the central part of the Gulf of Cazonés.

Next, from south to west, the underwater relief of the Batabanó Gulf has some irregularities due to the existence of cays and shoals with depths between 2–5m (Figure 3). In the central part, the underwater relief of the gulf is gentle, with maximum depths between 6–7m, and a shallow slope. In the

Figure 2. Analysis of the mean sea surface temperature in Cuban waters with the GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product in the Caribbean Sea and the Gulf of Mexico⁵: a) distribution of the annual mean, b) distribution in the dry season, c) distribution in the wet season.

Figure 3. Bathymetry of the seawaters around Cuba taken from the GEBCO Bathymetric Compilation Group¹³ under GEBCO 2018 Licence.

westernmost area of the southern portion, from Guano del Este Cay to San Antonio Cape, the slope of the island platform of Cuba falls abruptly towards great depths, finding in many places an isobath of 1,000m very close to the edge of the platform. Finally, the southern and southeastern coasts of Isla de la Juventud, with steep cliffs, drop abruptly to abyssal depths of 3,000m¹².

Computation of thermal efficiency

In the most feasible marine areas for the operation of OTEC plants, the average surface temperature of each year is approximately 26.7 to 29.4°, with cold water available at 4.4° or less at a depth of 900–1000m¹⁴. Therefore, even without the inevitable reduction caused by friction and heat loss, the maximum efficiency achieved by heat conversion in an OTEC plant can be achieved with a very small rate of energy production. To apply the calculation of thermal efficiency, the approach proposed in the research carried out in was considered, which is based on a theoretical limit, up to a maximum efficiency of an OTEC system through the conversion of heat into mechanical work stored in the warm surface waters of the tropical oceans:

$$\eta = \frac{T_w - T_c}{T_w}$$

Where η : thermal efficiency.

T_w : hot water temperature.

T_c : cold water temperature.

The calculation was made with a fixed longitude: moving in latitude to the north from the north coast of the archipelago and moving in latitude to the south from the south coast¹⁵.

Data validation

The MODIS Aqua Level 3 dataset encompasses sea surface temperature (SST) information derived from the NASA MODIS sensor situated on the Aqua satellite. SST data were extracted from the thermal infrared spectrum with wavelengths of 11 and 12 μm . After processing, the data is projected onto a cylindrical equidistant map with spatial bins measuring either 4.63 or 9.26 kilometers. This mapping method offers a comprehensive perspective of SST variations across diverse geographical areas¹⁶.

The World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) program was an ambitious international oceanographic research initiative conducted in the 1990s. With the participation of multiple countries and scientific organizations, the WOCE has focused on mapping and understanding global ocean circulation in detail. Fundamental technical data were collected through an extensive network of buoys, floats, and research vessel expeditions, including measurements of temperature, salinity, ocean currents, and sea level across the oceans. These data provide crucial information for understanding weather patterns, heat distribution on Earth, and ocean current variability, contributing significantly to the improvement of global climate models^{17,18}.

The *GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product* is a reanalysis dataset; therefore, it must be validated against observed datasets, and the quality information document for this product must be reviewed¹⁹. For surface validation, DSCompare v2.1 software was used²⁰, and the SST was validated using the Mann-Whitney statistical test comparing the global-reanalysis-phy-001-030 product with the observed MODIS Aqua level 3 and WOCE datasets. In both comparisons,

no significant differences were found throughout the Caribbean Sea and Gulf of Mexico (Figure 4); the significance level used was 0.05.

Drévilion¹⁹ performed several validations of the GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 reanalysis product, it has regional biases of less than 0.4 °C in temperature with respect to the World Ocean Atlas 2013 climatology (comparisons were made near surface, 100m, 300m, 500m, 800m, and 2000m depth) and to in situ observed data; the computed bias was less than 0.1 °C global mean with respect to in situ temperatures. The largest biases occurred in the 50–100m layer north of the Atlantic Ocean. The thermal structure improved significantly after 2002 with the deployment of Argo buoys, mainly at depths shallower than 300m, with an RMSE versus all in situ observations of less than 1°C and a bias close to 0°C and. The RMSE also decreases with time as a function of the density of the network of observations¹⁹. The differences between the GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product and observations show that the reanalysis is very stable over the period 2000–2016. There is a small bias of 0 - 0.1°C located between 100 and 200m. This reanalysis product outperforms climatology in terms of bias and RMS, with lower RMS differences in the 0–500m layer¹⁹. In addition, comparisons of this product with observed data from the CORA5 dataset^{21,22} and other sources in the years 1993, 1998, 2003, 2008, 2013, and 2016 showed that the mean differences tended to 0 °C in the Caribbean region.

The thermal efficiency of the ocean is closely linked to the heat exchange between the atmosphere and ocean. Large SST anomalies indicate significant deviations from their mean values, which can lead to a more substantial heat exchange; thus,

the accuracy of the thermal efficiency computation can be affected. Large SST anomalies can also trigger feedback mechanisms in the climate system, further complicating the computation of ocean thermal efficiency. For example, a positive SST anomaly can lead to increased evaporation, which in turn affects heat fluxes and vertical temperature variation in the oceans. These anomalies can also affect ocean circulation patterns. These changes affect heat transport within the ocean, which in turn influences the computation of thermal efficiency.

Figure 5 shows the minimum and maximum SST anomalies. The variability of the SST is greater in shallow waters, mainly in the gulfs (Guacanayabo, Batabano, and Ana Maria; see Figure 3), and in the archipelagos of southern and northern Cuba. In these areas, the depth is less than 763m, so this dataset does not provide thermal efficiency data. In the Bahama Bank and in some areas of the Gulf of Mexico the same thing happens, the SST variability is large, but depths shallower than 763m predominate. The SST anomaly varies less (the temperature is more stable) in the Caribbean Sea, in northern areas of Cuba (eastern and western part), in the Yucatan Channel, and in the Windward Passage (Figure 3), where the depth is greater than 763m; therefore, the value of the thermal efficiency is quite accurate. The north of the central part of Cuba, north of the archipelagos (St. Nicolas Channel and Old Bahama Channel; see Figure 3), the temperature is more stable, but the depth does not reach 763m.

Dataset

The database for the calculation of thermal efficiency in the seas around Cuba is the result of an investigation conducted by¹. As shown in Figure 6, the dataset includes three folders

Figure 4. Validation of the SST of the GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product in the Caribbean Sea and the Gulf of Mexico through the spatial distribution of the p-values of the Mann-Whitney test for a significance level of 0.05: **a)** Comparison of the SST of the GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product with the SST of MODIS Aqua level 3 (Probability) and **b)** Comparison of the SST of the GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product with the SST of the WOCE dataset (Probability)²⁰.

Figure 5. SST anomaly in the seawaters around Cuba²³, extracted from the DACS-PHY dataset²⁴, and computed with the CalcPlotAnomaly algorithm²⁵. **a)** Minimum SST anomalies. **b)** Maximum SST anomalies. 763 m and 1062 m isobaths taken from the GEBCO Bathymetric Compilation Group¹³ under GEBCO 2018 Licence.

Figure 6. File distribution by directory.

that contain annual information on thermal efficiency from 1993 to 2019:

- (i) 27 files calculated for the 1062m depth level.
- (ii) 27 files, calculated for a depth level of 763m, and
- (iii) 27 files calculated for the 902m depth level.

Each of the 81 files is stored in comma-separated txt format and 162.68 MB in size.

The same nodes of the regular data mesh of the temperature files **global-reanalysis-phy-001-030-daily**¹ for the study area were downloaded from the Copernicus site, and the number of nodes was 145 × 67. A description of the fields of each file separated by commas that do not have a header is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Description of the fields of the output files of the calculation of thermal efficiency.

*When it is not possible to calculate the thermal efficiency, either because the point is on land or because the depth level does not exist, the value is -32767.

Description of field	Data type
Date	Date
Level	float
Longitude	float
Latitude	float
Thermal efficiency	float*

Ethics and consent

Ethics and consent were not required for this study

Data availability

The data is available on the Science Data Bank site. The site is free to download and use data sets respecting the corresponding data license.

Science Data Bank: **Thermal Efficiency Dataset Around Cuban Seas (TEDACS)** <https://doi.org/10.57760/sciencedb.10037>

This project contains the following data:

- *_1062.44_MaxEfficiency.txt
- *_763.333_MaxEfficiency.txt

- *_902.339_MaxEfficiency.txt

*Years: 1993, 1994, 1995 ... 2019

Data are made available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

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This article provides a detailed analysis of the potential for thermal energy from sea temperature gradients around Cuba, utilizing 27 years of daily data to calculate thermal efficiency at different depths. This long-term data analysis is significant for understanding the availability and variability of thermal energy resources. The study generates 81 files, meticulously recording dates, depths, coordinates, and thermal efficiencies, providing a valuable foundation for future energy planning and environmental impact assessments. Additionally, the research explores applications beyond electricity generation, such as desalination, refrigeration, and aquaculture, highlighting the versatility of thermal energy resources.

However, it must be noted that the calculation of thermal efficiency presented in the article is wrong. In reality, the maximum thermal efficiency of using sea temperature gradients, even under ideal conditions, is limited by the Carnot cycle efficiency and could not possibly reach around 80%. The author needs to reinforce their understanding of thermodynamics, particularly when dealing with temperature units. Kelvin and Celsius are two different temperature scales, differing in their reference points (zero points) and temperature intervals. The thermal efficiency values reported in the article require further validation and explanation to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Partly

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Ocean thermal energy conversion; energy system

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

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Hooi Siang Kang

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The research presents an exploration of Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) feasibility in Cuba's maritime surroundings, underpinned by bathymetric characterization and thermal efficiency computations. The dataset, compiled over 27 years utilizing Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS) data, offers insights into thermal efficiency across specific latitudinal and longitudinal bounds.

The dataset's creation is evidently meticulous based on reliable data sources. The inclusion of CMEMS global ocean reanalysis data ensures a reliable foundation for thermal efficiency calculations. Furthermore, the utilization of MODIS Aqua and WOCE datasets for validation enhances the reliability of the dataset. Protocols employed in the research exhibit its alignment with established practices in OTEC feasibility studies. The computation of thermal efficiency reflects sound scientific methodology. Moreover, the detailed description of methods enhances transparency and facilitates replication by other researchers. The dataset's usability and accessibility are comprehensively documented. Overall, the research provides a potentially valuable contribution to sustainable energy development.

The suggested improvements could include conducting sensitivity analyses to assess the impact of various parameters on thermal efficiency calculations. Additionally, detailing quality control measures and the potential impact of SST anomalies on thermal efficiency calculations, would further facilitate research endeavors in utilizing the dataset.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Ocean Engineering

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 17 May 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18168.r39145>

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Erfan Amini

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The authors present a valuable dataset for assessing the thermal efficiency potential in the seas surrounding Cuba, which can contribute to research on Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) technologies and renewable energy exploration in the region. However, there are some limitations and areas that require further clarification or improvement.

The introduction effectively establishes the context and significance of the research, highlighting the potential of OTEC as a renewable energy source. However, the authors could provide more background information on previous studies or datasets related to thermal efficiency in the region to better situate their work within the existing literature.

The methods section provides details on the study area, data sources, and the equation used for calculating thermal efficiency. However, there are some limitations and uncertainties associated with the methodology that should be discussed. For example, the authors used reanalysis data with a spatial resolution of $1/12^\circ$, which may not capture local variations in thermal efficiency.

The authors performed data validation using statistical tests to compare the reanalysis data with observed datasets. While this is a useful step, the validation could be more comprehensive. For instance, the authors could compare their thermal efficiency results with any available in-situ measurements or other published datasets in the region to further validate their findings.

The dataset is well-organized and made publicly available, which is commendable. The figures and tables are informative and support the text. However, some figures, such as the SST trend map (Figure 1) and the spatial distribution of SST (Figure 2), could benefit from a more detailed interpretation and discussion of their implications for thermal efficiency calculations.

Overall Evaluation: The paper presents a valuable dataset for assessing the thermal efficiency potential in the seas around Cuba. The methodology is generally sound, and the data validation steps enhance the credibility of the results. However, the authors should address the limitations and uncertainties associated with their methodology and dataset more thoroughly. This would help users better understand the potential drawbacks and make informed decisions when using the dataset for their specific applications.

Suggestions for Improvement:

- Discuss the limitations and uncertainties associated with the spatial and temporal resolution of the reanalysis data and how they may impact the accuracy of the thermal efficiency calculations.
- Provide more background information on previous studies or datasets related to thermal efficiency in the region to better contextualize the current work.
- Expand the data validation by comparing the thermal efficiency results with any available in-situ measurements or other published datasets in the region.
- Provide a more detailed interpretation and discussion of the implications of the SST trend map and spatial distribution of SST for thermal efficiency calculations.
- Discuss the potential limitations and uncertainties associated with the dataset and how they may affect its usability for different applications.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Ocean Renewable Energy, Desing Optimization, Coastal Infrastructures

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 18 May 2024

Alejandro Rodriguez

Dear Reviewer Erfan Amini, Thank you very much for your time for reviewing and suggestioning. Comments regarding the limitations of the spatial and temporal resolution of the data used in the research will be added in the next version of the article and mention will be made of previous studies in the area (there are really few). We will also expand the

discussion of the implications of the sea surface temperature trend, and work to show the limitations associated with the data set. Thanks a lot.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 16 May 2024

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Dodi Sofyan Arief

Universitas Riau, Pekanbaru,, Indonesia

Abdul Khair Junaidi

Mechanical Engineering, Technology College of Pekanbaru, Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia

1. How was the process of calculating thermal efficiency conducted in this study?
2. Why were depths of 763, 902, and 1062 meters chosen as the focus of research for exploiting sea thermal energy?
3. What insights can be gained from the presented dataset regarding the potential development of renewable energy in the vicinity of Cuba?
4. What is the data quality of the Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS) GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 product used in this research?
5. What are the potential implications of the thermal efficiency findings from this research on the energy industry and environment in Cuba or surrounding regions?
6. What potential future research directions or areas can be developed based on the findings of this research data in the context of OTEC system development?

The literature review is not sufficient for the given title. Try to expand the reviewed references by prioritizing publications. The following papers are just suggestions and can help improve the given discussion:

(Koto, 2012) (Ref-1)

(Koto et al.,2017)(Ref-2)

(Koto et al.,2016)(Ref-3)

(Koto et al.,2012)(Ref-4)

References

1. J, Kato: Potential of Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion in Indonesia.
<https://isomase.org/IJERCE/Vol.4%20Oct%202016/4-1.pdf>.
2. J. Koto A, Tasri K, Insannual D, Arief Efiufrizal, et al.: Sea Temperatures Profiles for Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion in Siberut-Mentawai, Sumatera Barat, Indonesia.
<https://isomase.org/JSOse/Vol.11%20Sep%202017/11-2.pdf>.

3. J, Koto N, Ridho: Preliminary Study on Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion in Siberut Island, West Sumatera, Indonesia. <https://isomase.org/JAse/Vol.6%20May%202016/6-1.pdf>.

4. J, Koto D, arief A, Tasri I, et al.: Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion in Indonesia, Malaysia and Philippines. <https://isomase.org/Journals/index.php/ijerce/article/view/94/70>.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Ocean thermal energy conversion (OTEC) is a renewable energy technology (Mechanical Engineering)

We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however we have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 18 May 2024

Alejandro Rodriguez

Dear Dodi Sofyan Arief

We thank you for taking your time to review our article.

All your comments, suggestions and bibliographic references suggested by the reviewer will be taken into account in the next version of the article.

We will take all the questions you have asked into account for version 2 of the manuscript.

We truly believe that it will raise its scientific level. We will study and use, in the new version, the suggested bibliography.

Thank you so much.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.